

Best Practice Document

Best Practice for the Collection, Processing and Storage of Human Samples

Part 2: Collecting Urine Samples

Annex 2.2 to AD4.1

WP 4 – T4.1

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Acronyms

CDC	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
DINCH	Diisononyl 1,2-cyclohexanedicarboxylic acid
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HBM4EU	European Human Biomonitoring Initiative
ID	Identifier
LOQ	Limit of Quantification
PARC	European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals
PP	Polypropylene
QA	Quality assurance
QC	Quality control
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
WHO	World Health Organization

1. Introduction

This part of the “Best Practice for the Collection, Processing and Storage of Human Samples” provides detailed instructions for the collection of urine samples (first morning urine) to be used in PARC. Please read carefully “PART 1 – General instructions” of this SOP before starting the collection of human samples – especially the following chapters:

- Precautions in the pre-analytical phase
- Preparations for sampling including pre-treatment of vessels and cryovials
- Field blanks
- Sample conservation, storage & shipment

General recommendations for the collection of human samples can be found in CDC (2018) [1].

2. Sampling

Collection and processing of the urine samples according to the PARC specifications is a very important step. If samples are not correctly collected and processed, the analytical results may not be precise or valid. According to the [PARC General Survey Design](#), urine samples from following age groups are expected to be collected in each study:

Target Group	Biological Material	Sample type to be collected
Children 6 -11 years	Urine	first morning urine
Teenagers 12 - 17 years	Urine	first morning urine
Adults 18 - 39 years	Urine	first morning urine

Urine samples (first morning urine) should be collected from each participant.

2.1. Samples to be collected

Best practice:

To guarantee the comparability of analytical results **first morning urine (entire bladder emptying) should be collected**. Only if not possible, the collection of spot urine samples should be considered. Quality-assured analysis of creatinine and specific gravity as a measure for urinary dilution were defined as obligatory for all urine samples to enable normalization and hence comparability of analytical results between the different studies.

Critical remark:

A spot urine sample reflects only a specific point in time and does not provide information on the exposure of an entire day. If spot urine samples are collected, the concentration of the target biomarker may be below the LOQ due to sample dilution or could be overestimated due to the short time between ingestion and excretion.

In order to avoid background contaminations resulting from the manufacturing process, all vessels and cryovials should **cleaned according to a standardized protocol** of be carried out. Please follow the instructions described in Part 1 of this Best Practice.

The number of aliquots will depend on different aspects among them the target group, number of target chemicals, the number of analyses or the LOQ of the analytical method employed. Hence, the following information should be clearly defined in a study protocol (see PARC general survey design):

- required number of aliquots per sample
- needed volume for each sample
- information that should be provided on the label
- storage temperature

Based to the most recent status of the discussion the following biomarkers will be analysed in urine samples:

- Metals (Arsenic and its compounds, Cadmium, Chrome, Mercury and its organic compound)
- Bisphenols
- Phthalate metabolites and DINCH metabolites
- Pesticides (Pyrethroids, Neonicotinoids (Acetamiprid), Organophosphates (chlorpyrifos))
- Cotinine
- Creatinine

To allow for the analysis of additional biomarkers of future interest, further aliquots per sample should be generated in addition to the aliquots for the above biomarkers, depending on the consent and the ethics vote. Considering the number of biomarkers already confirmed for analysis (6), we recommend generating at least 15 aliquots per first morning urine sample if a sufficient amount of urine is available. Depending on the final number of biomarkers, aliquots of field blank samples should be generated as described in Part 1 to allow for the documentation and assessment of any background contamination.

Table 1: Overview – Aliquots to be collected

Age group	Sample Type	Number of Aliquots	Volume of Aliquots	Aliquots for already confirmed biomarker	Aliquots for additional analysis
Children	morning urine	15	4 mL	8	7
Teenagers	morning urine	15	4 mL	7	8
Adults	morning urine	15	4 mL	7	8
Children	field blank*	15**	4 mL	8	7
Teenagers	field blank*	15**	4 mL	7	8
Adults	field blank*	15**	4 mL	7	8

* Best practice: From 10 % of the total number of participants for each sample type (see Part 1 of this Best Practice Document)

**depending on the final number target biomarker/analysis

2.2. Material needed for urine collection, processing and storage

2.2.1. Morning urine collection

- Urine collection vessels (sterile, at least 500 ml, made of polypropylene with a screw cap, pre-treated to eliminate possible contaminants)
- Plastic hermetic bags (e.g., black, non-transparent) to place the urine vessels inside
- If required textile bags for transporting the sample to the study center or laboratory
- Labels that contain at least the following information:
 - identification number (Participant-ID)
- Sampling instructions for volunteers (see page 6) with information on who participants can contact if they need additional information or help
- Urine samples related sampling questionnaire (see page 6)
- Field blanks (PART 1 – General Instructions)

2.2.2. Processing and storage of first morning urine samples

- Safety equipment according to biological safety level 2 (BSL2) containment (e.g., lab coat, powder-free disposable latex or similar gloves, safety glasses)
- Surface & hand disinfectant
- 10 x 4 mL pre-cleaned cryovials (polypropylene) per participant/field blank
- Cryovial racks
- Pens
- Biohazard waste containers
- Storage boxes (cryoboxes) for the sample and field blank aliquots
- -80 °C electrical freezers or liquid nitrogen storage infrastructure

- Pipettes/multipettes/dispensettes with corresponding tips (RNase-free, 5 mL)
- Density meter to measure urine density of each sample
- Labels with the assigned identification number suitable for temperatures down to -80 °C or -196 °C depending on the used freezing technology. These include:
 - labels for storage boxes
 - labels for cryovials for aliquots of all samples including the field blank aliquots
 - labels for the field blanks (QA)

Note: All used material must be precisely labeled throughout sampling and handling stages to ensure adequate labeling. Pre-labeling of cryovials is recommended.

2.3. Collection of urine samples

Best practice:

Prior to sampling, each participant should receive an **urine collection kit** with the materials listed above and a detailed written instruction how to collect the urine sample. A step-by-step sampling instruction for the participants can be found below. Ideally, the first morning urine sample should be collected on the same day as the blood collection and the interview takes place.

Prior to sampling, each participant must be informed about:

- goals of the study,
- declaration of consent process,
- sampling procedures (and related risks),
- pseudonymised data & sample processing, and
- data management, -processing & -storage.

Field blanks should be generated according to the description in PART 1 - General Instructions and included in the analyses of each target biomarker.

2.3.1. Matrix-specific questionnaire accompanying the sampling of urine

Urine sampling should be accompanied by the collection of some basic information related to the urine sample and relevant information necessary for data interpretation. For a standardized data record, please use the “[Matrix-specific questionnaire accompanying the sampling of urine](#)”.

2.3.2. How to collect first morning urine – an instruction for participants

What to do:

Please read carefully these step-by-step instructions before taking the urine sample. Collect your complete **first morning urine sample** according to this instruction on the agreed day. If this is not possible or if you have any questions, please contact the study team. Contact details are provided at the end of this instruction.

Supplies needed:

- provided urine collection vessel
- label with the assigned personal identification number
- permanent marker to complete the label with the required information (date & time of urine sample collection)
- plastic bag for temporarily storage of your sample until handover

Collect your **first morning urine sample** immediately after getting up. Do not use another vessel than the one provided. Please do not rinse out the vessel with e.g., tap water before taking the sample. In order to maintain sample integrity ideally urine should be collected in a clean and dust-free environment. In order to protect your confidentiality, please do not write your name anywhere on the collection kit.

- When you first wake up, go to the bathroom.
- Wash your hands carefully.
- Do not remove the cap from the urine vessel until ready to collect.
- The inside of the vessel and cap should not touch or come into contact with any part of your body, clothing, or external surfaces.
- Open the vessel and place the screw cap with the top side down to avoid external contamination from dust.
- Urinate the full void morning urine into the provided vessel until you have completely emptied your bladder. Do not overfill the vessel: if the vessel is too small for all your urine, please stop before overfilling.
- Screw the cap and make sure it is tightly closed to prevent leakage.
- Note date and time of the urine collection on the provided label.
- Stick the label properly on urine vessel as demonstrated in the figure.
- Immediately after collection, place the urine vessel into the provided plastic bag and keep the sample at 4-8 °C until you hand it over to the study team. Ideally, this should be done within 24 h.
- Please complete the sampling questionnaire.
- Any questions? Please contact our study team (please provide respective contact information, e.g., phone number, email address)

3. Sample processing and storage

For further sample processing, urine samples should be transferred in a cool box to the laboratory as fast as possible.

Best practice:

Sample transfer and processing should be done within on the same day as sample collection. Ideally, samples should be processed and frozen within 24 hours.

Note: If samples cannot be processed within 24h, please freeze samples and store until processing at -20 °C. Avoid long-term storage at -20 °C.

3.1. Urine sample processing

Please ensure that all necessary material for sample processing is available (see page 5) and check if all cryovials are properly labelled (see PART 1 – General Instructions). Receipt of samples in the laboratory (date, time) and sample condition must be documented. If direct processing of the samples is not possible, store the sample at 4-8°C until further processing. Ideally, samples should be processed within 24h after collection.

3.1.1. Homogenization of urine samples

Please check if the urine collection vessel is well closed! Swivel the well closed urine collection vessel carefully with the lid downwards for a short time and then swivel again with the lid upwards in slightly circular movements. Aliquot the homogenized samples rapidly.

3.1.2. Aliquoting

Before aliquoting, urine samples should be homogenized by swiveling the vessel carefully. Generate at least 15 aliquots per sample as follows and document any relevant information in the sample processing protocol:

- 7-8 aliquots of 4 mL urine for:
 - bisphenols (children, teenager, adults)
 - metals (arsenic and its compounds, Cd, Cr, mercury and its organic compound) (children, teenager)
 - pesticides – glyphosate/AMPA (adults)
 - pesticides – pyrethroids (children, teenager, adults)
 - pesticides – neonicotinoids (acetamiprid) (children, adults)
 - pesticides – organophosphates (chlorpyrifos) (children, teenager, adults)
 - phthalate metabolites and DINCH metabolites (children, teenager)
 - creatinine (children, teenager, adults)
 - cotinine (children, teenager, adults)
- 7-8 aliquots of 4 mL urine for further investigations.

A **protocol** should specify the exact procedure including the needed volume and the order in which the aliquots should be collected. This protocol should also specify analytical priority in case the volume of the sample is not sufficient for all planned analyses. This is particularly important when collecting samples from children or older adults.

3.1.3. Measurement of urinary specific gravity

If sufficient urine is available after aliquoting, use the remaining urine to measure **urinary density** of the urine sample. **Specific gravity** can be calculated based on the measured density values divided by the density of a standard or reference (usually: density of water 0,998 g/cm³) if the device is not able to put out these data directly.

Best practice:

Use an electronic density measurement device (density meter). Please use only validated and calibrated devices and document validation and calibration results for QA/QC purposes.

Do not use urine test strips as they do not give the accurate value needed for normalization.

For the documentation of individual sample processing steps a detailed **process protocol** should be filled. The following table shows an example how such a protocol could be designed. such a protocol can be used to document whether all expected samples per participant have been collected, processed, and frozen or for which participant this is not the case as part of the routine QA/QC procedure.

Table 2: Protocol on sample processing – Example

Participant	Arrival in the laboratory		Aliquots for analysis number	Aliquots for storage number	Specific gravity accuracy of 3 decimals	Storage		Processed by	Notes
	Date [dd.mm.yyyy]	Time [hh:mm]				Date [dd.mm.yyyy]	Time [hh:mm]		
001	-----	__:--			-.----	-----	__:--		
002	-----	__:--			-.----	-----	__:--		
003	-----	__:--			-.----	-----	__:--		

3.2. Urine aliquot storage

Best practice:

Immediately after processing, the generated aliquots should be stored at **-80 °C or lower** until further analysis or any other purpose (e.g., transfer to PARC partner or laboratory) (PART 1 - General Instructions).

4. Transport of samples to laboratories

A shipping date should be arranged between the sample collector and the laboratories for the planned analyses. When arrangements have been finalized, the addressees should be informed of the time and means of transportation.

All information related to a proper transport of the samples in human biomonitoring studies is given in the HBM4EU SOP “Strategy and SOPs for human sample exchange, including ethical demands”. This includes:

- Shipping Category B Biological Substances
- Pro-Forma Invoice
- Sample Transfer Protocol (Manifest)
- Data Transfer Template
- Material and Data Transfer Agreement
- Documents can be downloaded from the [HBM4EU document library](#).

5. Tailored sampling protocol

Preparations for sampling vessels

Urine collection in **sterile, screw-capped polypropylene vessels** of sufficient volume to empty the entire bladder (**500 mL** for adults)

Pre-treatment of vessels for sampling and storage

→ Rinse all vessels including the caps

→ Leave the vessels and lid to dry upside down on a clean filter paper or in a safety cabinet (class 2)

→ Close the vessels and put into a zip-lock plastic bag

PARC

Preparations for sampling cryovials

Sampling aliquot into **sterile cryovials** made of medical grade **polypropylene**, free of leachable, heavy metals, and DNase/RNase suitable for the used storage technology

Pre-treatment of cryovials for sampling and storage

→ Rinse all cryovials including the caps

→ Leave the cryovials to dry in their respective racks, upside down, in a safety cabinet (class 2)

→ Close the cryovials in the safety cabinet

PARC

Preparations for sampling

Labelling

All **used material** must be **precisely labelled**: vessels, cryovials, freezer boxes...
Pre-labelling of collection vessels with at least the participant ID.

Minimum information on the cryovials that must be readable with electronic barcode readers

General survey	Country ID	Target group ID	Biological matrix ID	Participant ID	Aliquot ID
G	- XX	- X	- XX	- XXX	- XXX
	2-digit abbreviation code according to ISO 3166	Children: C Teenagers: T Adults: A	Morning urine: UM Spot urine: US	3-digit number of participant in each country	

Note

In studies where multiple aliquots are required for different analyses, a sample collection protocol should specify the exact procedure including the needed volume and the order in which the aliquots should be collected. This protocol should also specify analytical priority in case the volume of the sample is not sufficient for all planned analyses. To allow for the analysis of additional biomarkers of future interest, further aliquots per sample should be generated in addition to the aliquots for the analysis of defined biomarkers depending on the consent and the ethics vote.

PARC

Urine sampling

Instructions for participants

Each participant should receive an **urine collection kit** and a detailed **written instruction for urine collection**

- Urine collection vessel
- Label with the assigned personal identification number
- Permanent marker to complete the label
- Plastic bag for temporarily storage

Collect your **first morning urine** sample **immediately after getting up**
 Use only the vessel provided
 Do not rinse out the vessel before taking the sample

1. Wash your hands carefully
2. Do not remove the cap from the urine vessel until ready to collect the sample
3. Ensure that the inside of the vessel and cap do not touch any part of your body, clothing, or external surfaces
4. Open the vessel and place the screw cap top side down
5. Urinate until your bladder is completely emptied, but stop before overfilling the vessel
6. Screw the cap on tightly to ensure it is securely closed
7. Record the date and time on the provided label
8. Stick the label as demonstrated in the figure
9. Place the vessel into the plastic bag and store it at 4-8°C until you hand it over to the study team (ideally within 24 hours)
10. Complete the sampling questionnaire

PARC

Urine sampling

Instructions for field blanks

- 1** Prepare the **field blank vessel** with half of the volume with **ultra-pure water** (18.2 MΩcm) **at the sampling site** in a laminar flow safety cabinet/work bench
- 2** Provide the **prepared field blank vessel** in addition to the urine sampling vessel to **10%** (minimum 2%) **of the study participants**

Instruction for the participant

1. Take both the urine sampling vessel and the field blank vessel to the bathroom
2. Open the field blank vessel at the same time as the urine sampling vessel
3. Leave the field blank vessel open while collecting your urine sample
4. Close the field blank vessel securely once you have finished
5. Write the date and time on the label for both vessels

PARC

Urine sampling

PARC

Urine aliquoting

Children	Teenagers	Adults
Target biomarker in PARC		
Bisphenols	Bisphenols	Bisphenols
Metals Cd, Cr, Mercury and its organic compound	Arsenic and its organic compounds	Cd
Pesticides – Pyrethroids	Pesticides – Pyrethroids	Pesticides – Glyphosate/AMPA
Pesticides – Neonicotinoids		Pesticides – Pyrethroids
Pesticides – Organophosphates	Pesticides – Organophosphates	Pesticides – Neonicotinoids
Phtalate metabolites and DINCH metabolites	Phtalate metabolites and DINCH metabolites	Pesticides – Organophosphates
Creatinine	Creatinine	Creatinine
Cotonine	Cotonine	Cotonine
Effect biomarker in PARC (optional)		
NAG, A1MG, creatinine, albumin, Kim-1, RBP4		
8OHdG, 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine		8OHdG, 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine

PARC

References

1. CDC, *Improving the Collection and Management of Human Samples Used for Measuring Environmental Chemicals and Nutrition Indicators*. 2018, U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.